

Supplementary Materials

Design, Synthesis, Biological Evaluation and in silico studies of 2-anilino-4- (benzimidazol-1-yl)pyrimidine Scaffold as Anti-tumor Agents.

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3-((4-(1H-benzod[imidazol-1-yl]pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4a):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4a)

LCMS spectra of compound (4a)

Peak No	RT (min)	Area	Area %
1	3.335	2.123e3	99.115
2	3.402	18.948	0.885

HPLC spectra of compound (4a)

	Peak Name	RT	Area (μV*sec)	% Area
1	Peak1	3.868	226535	4.28
2	Peak2	10.069	11678	0.22
3	Peak3	10.746	5040921	95.26
4	Peak4	11.485	12409	0.23
Sum			5291542.3	100.0

3-((4-(1H-benzod[imidazol-1-yl]-5-fluoropyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4b):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4b)

LCMS spectra of compound (4b)

HPLC spectra of compound (4b)

	RT	Area (μV*sec)	% Area
1	8.691	72215	0.69
2	9.778	7952	0.08
3	13.105	10367227	99.04
4	18.444	20256	0.19
Sum		10467649.1	100.0

3-((4-(1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)-5-methylpyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4c):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4c)

LCMS spectra of compound (4c)

Peak No	RT min	Area	Area %
1	3.717	6.641e3	99.174
2	3.867	55.305	0.826

HPLC spectra of compound (4c)

Signal 1:DAD1, Sig=250.00, 2.00 Ref=off, EXT

Peak #	RT [min]	Name	Area	Height	Area %
1	10.839		7.9	1.293	0.19
2	11.765		23.8	2.450	0.57
3	12.079		5.0	1.498	0.12
4	12.240		4023.5	554.234	97.38
5	12.507		7.6	1.888	0.18
6	13.089		63.9	9.199	1.55

3-((4-(1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)-5-(trifluoromethyl)pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4d):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4d)

LCMS spectra of compound (4d)

Peak No	RT min	Area	Area %
1	3.378	5.289e3	98.624
2	3.519	52.120	0.972
3	3.671	21.659	0.404

HPLC spectra of compound (4d)

Signal 1:DAD1 A, Sig=220,4 Ref=off

Peak #	RT [min]	Name	Area	Area %
1	3.391		9.4	0.26
2	4.698		12.1	0.34
3	4.954		3527.2	98.87
4	12.325		18.8	0.53

3-((4-(2-methyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4e):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4e)

LCMS spectra of compound (4e)

Peak No	RT (min)	Area	Area %
1	3.706	4.261e3	98.986
2	5.022	43.630	1.014

HPLC spectra of compound (4e)

Signal 1:DAD1 A, Sig=220,4 Ref=off

Peak #	RT [min]	Name	Area	Area %
1	8.713		37.4	0.92
2	8.900		25.8	0.63
3	9.388		4002.3	98.45

3-((5-fluoro-4-(2-methyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4f):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4f)

LCMS spectra of compound (4f)

HPLC spectra of compound (4f)

Signal 1:DAD1 A, Sig=220,4 Ref=off

Peak #	RT [min]	Name	Area	Height	Area %
1	10.112		90.3	14.719	1.70
2	10.422		5229.0	802.217	98.30

3-((5-methyl-4-(2-methyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4g):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4g)

LCMS spectra of compound (4g)

Peak No	RT min	Area	Area %
1	3.539	4.615e3	98.551
2	3.795	67.858	1.449

HPLC spectra of compound (4g)

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Signal 1 : DAD1 A, Sig=220,4 Ref=off

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Peak #	RT [min]	Name	Height	Area	Area %
1	9.067		1.346e3	8887.6	99.29
2	9.763		4.841	34.1	0.38
3	13.310		4.159	29.3	0.33

3-((4-(2-methyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)-5-(trifluoromethyl)pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4h):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4h)

LCMS spectra of compound (4h)

HPLC spectra of compound (4h)

Signal 1:DAD1, Sig=252.00, 2.00 Ref=off, EXT

Peak #	RT [min]	Name	Area	Height	Area %
1	6.100		4.5	0.648	0.12
2	7.048		18.2	21.996	0.46
3	7.138		3905.5	556.631	99.25
4	7.413		4.3	1.446	0.11
5	7.913		2.7	0.371	0.07

3-((4-(2-(trifluoromethyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4i):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4i)

LCMS spectra of compound (4i)

HPLC spectra of compound (4i)

Signal 1:DAD1 A, Sig=220,4 Ref=off

Peak #	RT [min]	Name	Area	Height	Area %
1	13.222		27.5	4.118	0.42
2	13.887		6557.0	911.340	99.58

3-((5-fluoro-4-(2-(trifluoromethyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4j):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4j)

LCMS spectra of compound (4j)

Peak No	RT min	Area	Area %
1	4.264	1.690e3	99.159
2	4.332	14.339	0.841

HPLC spectra of compound (4j)

Signal 1:DAD1, Sig=234.00, 2.00 Ref=off, EXT

Peak #	RT [min]	Name	Area	Height	Area %
1	11.612		27.3	3.965	0.46
2	13.266		7.8	1.097	0.13
3	14.599		11.7	1.582	0.20
4	14.885		5916.3	836.687	99.22

3-((5-methyl-4-(2-(trifluoromethyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4k):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4k)

LCMS spectra of compound (4k)

Peak No	RT min	Area	Area %
1	3.734	3.793e3	99.394
2	4.657	23.120	0.606

HPLC spectra of compound (4k)

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Signal 1 : DAD1 A, Sig=220,4 Ref=off

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Peak #	RT [min]	Name	Height	Area	Area %
1	3.114		0.716	4.5	0.12
2	3.856		466.525	3896.6	99.88

3-((5-(trifluoromethyl)-4-(2-(trifluoromethyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4l):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4l)

LCMS spectra of compound (4I)

HPLC spectra of compound (4I)

Signal 1:DAD1, Sig=260.00, 2.00 Ref=off, EXT

Peak #	RT [min]	Name	Area	Height	Area %
1	3.375		7.1	1.174	0.05
2	3.655		29.6	5.079	0.22
3	4.548		105.3	9.953	0.77
4	4.682		13423.7	1.563e3	98.31
5	5.036		82.2	7.552	0.60
6	6.437		6.4	0.903	0.05

3-((4-(2-isopropyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4m):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4m)

LCMS spectra of compound (4m)

Peak No	RT min	Area	Area %
1	3.747	88.175	1.344
2	4.197	6.474e3	98.656

HPLC spectra of compound (4m)

Signal 1:DAD1 A, Sig=220,4 Ref=off

Peak #	RT [min]	Name	Area	Area %
1	11.044		124.0	1.76
2	11.382		6936.9	98.24

3-((5-fluoro-4-(2-isopropyl-1H-benzodimidazol-1-yl)pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4n):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4n)

LCMS spectra of compound (4n)

Peak No	RT (min)	Area	Area %
1	3.640	2.198e3	98.801
2	4.682	26.664	1.199

HPLC spectra of compound (4n)

Signal 1 : DAD1 A, Sig=220,4 Ref=off

Peak #	RT [min]	Name	Height	Area	Area %
1	13.068		2.703	19.1	0.53
2	13.320		514.925	3561.3	98.42
3	14.328		6.524	38.1	1.05

3-((4-(2-isopropyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)-5-methylpyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4o):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4o)

LCMS spectra of compound (4o)

HPLC spectra of compound (4o)

	RT	Area (μV*sec)	% Area
1	10.993	9930044	99.62
2	11.200	14004	0.14
3	11.367	14040	0.14
4	12.017	9734	0.10
Sum		9967821.4	100.0

3-((4-(2-isopropyl-1H-benzodimidazol-1-yl)-5-(trifluoromethyl)pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4p):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4p)

LCMS spectra of compound (4p)

HPLC spectra of compound (4p)

Signal 1:DAD1, Sig=254.00, 2.00 Ref=off, EXT

Peak #	RT [min]	Name	Area	Area %
1	5.011		9.1	0.24
2	5.097		38.6	1.00
3	5.265		3736.9	96.48
4	5.590		2.6	0.07
5	6.011		5.8	0.15
6	6.587		3.2	0.08
7	6.734		7.8	0.20
8	6.938		10.5	0.27
9	8.086		24.1	0.62
10	8.262		20.4	0.53
11	10.362		8.4	0.22
12	11.120		5.8	0.15

3-((4-(2-cyclopropyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4q):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4q)

LCMS spectra of compound (4q)

Peak No	RT min	Area	Area %
1	1.017	119.906	1.670
2	3.487	97.447	1.357
3	4.004	6.936e3	96.618
4	5.050	25.412	0.354

HPLC spectra of compound (4q)

Signal 1:DAD1, Sig=248.00, 2.00 Ref=off, EXT

Peak #	RT [min]	Name	Area	Area %
1	8.282		73.0	1.69
2	9.661		6.0	0.14
3	10.369		62.5	1.45
4	10.512		27.2	0.63
5	11.082		7.7	0.18
6	11.420		4116.9	95.54
7	12.049		16.0	0.37

3-((4-(2-cyclopropyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)-5-fluoropyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4r):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4r)

LCMS spectra of compound (4r)

HPLC spectra of compound (4r)

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Signal 1 : DAD1 A, Sig=220,4 Ref=off

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Peak #	RT [min]	Name	Height	Area	Area %
1	8.974		3.687	33.0	0.39
2	10.260		26.096	174.1	2.08
3	11.101		1.124e3	8165.9	97.53

3-((4-(2-cyclopropyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)-5-methylpyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4s):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4s)

LCMS spectra of compound (4s)

HPLC spectra of compound (4s)

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 Signal 1 : DAD1 A, Sig=220,4 Ref=off
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Peak #	RT [min]	Name	Height	Area	Area %
1	8.974		3.687	33.0	0.39
2	10.260		26.096	174.1	2.08
3	11.101		1.124e3	8165.9	97.53

3-((4-(2-cyclopropyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)-5-(trifluoromethyl)pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)benzenesulfonamide (4t):

¹H-NMR spectra of compound (4t)

LCMS spectra of compound (4t)

Peak No	RT min	Area	Area %
1	2.616	3.505e3	99.676
2	2.889	11.395	0.324

HPLC spectra of compound (4t)

	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	% Area
1	18.102	15292	0.26
2	18.269	16507	0.28
3	18.915	5915644	99.27
4	19.401	11645	0.20
Sum		5958988.4	100.0